

Building Intelligence Into Intelligent Buildings

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Most modern "Intelligent" buildings is focused on enhancing the users control when interacting with the building, and simplifying this interaction. BIIIB is different because it analyses its users and then take over the control of the building based on this analysis. First the system monitors its users normal interactions with the building, and once it has enough information it will begin to take over various tasks like for example controlling the lights.

We have implemented a simple AI which controls the lighting in the the ground floor hallway of building 322. This simplified implementation is made with a network of motion sensors along the hallway, and wireless lights switches, which allow our server, to control the lights. We have managed to cut the time the lamps are turned on in half, compared to the normal system, and this is done while actually increasing the comfort of the users*.

*that is excluding the entire development phases, and the endless amount of system crashes.